

27 **Abstract**

28 The degradation profile of Mg alloys in biomedical environments can be controlled by applying
29 various types of surface coatings. Phosphate chemical conversion coatings (CaP) and polylactic
30 acid (PLA) biopolymer coatings are biocompatible and promising for the corrosion protection of
31 Mg alloys. The aim of this work was to investigate the physicochemical properties and corrosion
32 performance of inorganic, organic, and mixed inorganic-organic coatings. Three types of surface
33 modification, CaP, PLA, and a combined CaP-PLA coating were obtained on the surface of the
34 magnesium alloy WE43. Scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, X-ray photoelectron
35 spectroscopy, and infrared spectroscopy were employed to characterize the surface and interfacial
36 morphology, along with the composition of the coatings before and after corrosion experiments.
37 The protective performance of obtained coatings was examined by electrochemical impedance
38 spectroscopy and immersion testing in Hank's solution. The results allowed to propose the
39 mechanism of the coatings growth and their further corrosion degradation. A two-component CaP-
40 PLA coating provided reliable corrosion resistance in Hank's solution for 14 days.

41

42 **Keywords:** Magnesium alloy; Polylactic Acid; Calcium Hydrogen Phosphate; Corrosion
43 Mechanism, Hank's Solution

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46 **1. Introduction**

47 The development of reliable metallic implant materials designed to replace bone tissue and
48 fix bone fractures gained immense scientific and practical interest. Such materials should combine
49 biological compatibility with human organisms and mechanical properties similar to those of
50 native bone tissue [1]. Modern metallic implants include commercially pure titanium, Ti-6Al-4V
51 alloy, 316L stainless steel, and cobalt-chromium alloys [2,3]. Due to the discrepancy between the
52 mechanical properties of a natural bone (Young's modulus 10–30 GPa) and implant materials
53 (Young's modulus 100–200 GPa) [4,5], the latter has a serious drawback called stress shielding
54 [6]. Insufficient load on healthy bone tissue leads to its resorption and loosening of the implant,
55 reducing its life. In addition, after bone healing, metal implants usually need to be removed within
56 two years of the first surgery [7,8], with medical, social, and economic consequences and costs
57 [9].

58 Another concept of biomedical materials includes biodegradable metallic implants. The
59 development and implementation of biodegradable implants is a promising way to eliminate the
60 problem of repeated surgical interventions [10–12]. In particular, magnesium is one of the best
61 materials for the manufacture of biodegradable implants. Biodegradation of Mg proceeds with
62 hydrogen depolarization and can lead to a violation of the mechanical integrity of the implant
63 before the bone heals. The main approaches to reduce the rate of biodegradation of Mg are alloying
64 and surface functionalization. Alloying with Zn, Ca, and Y significantly improves the mechanical
65 properties of Mg [13–16]. These elements also improve the corrosion resistance of magnesium
66 and, accordingly, reduce the rate of hydrogen evolution [17,18]. The Mg alloy WE43 is a high-
67 strength Mg alloy with Y and Nd as the main alloying elements. It has high creep resistance and
68 biocompatibility, suitable mechanical properties, and density close to those of native bone [19–
69 22]. Importantly, its corrosion products are nontoxic, and it does not contain Al, which is
70 considered to be neurotoxic and can cause dementia and Alzheimer's disease [23,24].

71 The main drawback of Mg-based materials is their rapid corrosion in biological media
72 [21,25,26]. Surface modification of Mg and its alloys is widely used to form functional coatings
73 for various purposes [21,25,27]. Conversion treatment is the most accessible and simple method
74 of the surface modification of metals [21,25,28]. In terms of biomedical applications, the most
75 common conversion coatings include phosphates, rare earth, Al-Mg layered double hydroxides,
76 and some organic polymers [27].

77 Phosphate chemical conversion treatment is a process in which a protective film is obtained
78 by the reaction of the Mg substrate with phosphating agents in the bath. To tune the coating
79 properties according to the target applications, the deposition bath is usually modified by adding
80 different cations [27,29]. In this manner it is possible to obtain coatings based on calcium
81 phosphates (CaP), which have high chemical resistance in biological media and excellent
82 biocompatibility and are osteoconductive and bioresorbable [27,30,31]. It is known [32,33], that
83 CaP conversion layers can reduce the corrosion rate of magnesium alloys by almost 10 times.
84 However, CaP layers formed on the surface of magnesium alloys often have inhomogeneous
85 morphology with many cracks and pores [34]. These pores originate from the release of hydrogen
86 bubbles from the magnesium substrate with the formation of a CaP layer around them.

87 Organic coatings provide more flexibility in terms of chemical functionalization of the
88 metal surface to mimic the multi-functional performance of the natural bone [35]. As organic
89 coatings on magnesium alloys, various biopolymers are used [35–39], whose mechanical
90 properties are comparable to those of soft biological tissues. In addition, polymer coatings can be
91 modified by multifunctional inhibitors or drug carriers [35,40],

92 Recently, biocompatible and bioresorbable polymers, such as polylactic acid (PLA) has
93 been extensively examined as a promising tool to modify biodegradable Mg-based materials [35].
94 It has been shown [38,41] that PLA coatings reduce the corrosion rate of magnesium and its alloys
95 in biological media. The deposition of a multilayer PLA coating on the AZ31 magnesium alloy
96 led to an increase in the polarization resistance R_p by almost 3.5 times. It has also been reported

97 [42], that the use of PLA to modify the magnesium surface significantly improves
98 cytocompatibility and reduces the release of Mg^{2+} ions during cell culture tests, which indicates
99 an increase in the corrosion resistance of the magnesium substrate.

100 Compared to single polymer layers, multilayer coatings consisting of inorganic and organic
101 layers showed higher anticorrosion efficiency [35,40,43–45]. Biopolymer supports cell growth,
102 biocompatibility, and controlled biodegradation, while the inorganic layer improves the
103 mechanical properties of the material (Young's modulus, compressive strength), bioactivity, and
104 osseointegration [46,47]. The combination of organic and inorganic layers makes it possible to
105 create new multifunctional materials for bioengineering.

106 Effectiveness of the corrosion protection of Mg alloys highly depends on their
107 microstructure and alloying elements [27,48–50]. In the case of conversion coatings, the
108 composition of the used substrate also plays an important role in the process of the coating
109 formation and its further corrosion performance [27,51]. To date, most studies on the development
110 of conversion coatings have been devoted to the AZ-series (Mg-Al-Zn) alloys [27,52], while the
111 information on the protection of the Mg-rare earth alloys, like WE43, is very limited. In most
112 cases, corrosion properties of the formed layers are evaluated in NaCl solutions and, less often, in
113 SBF solution [27,52]. However, the WE43 alloy is a promising candidate for biomedical
114 applications and examination of its corrosion in different biologically relevant media is of great
115 importance [53,54]. In our recent study [26] we have shown a significant difference in corrosion
116 mechanisms between the AZ31 and WE43 alloys in Hank's solution, with a more complex
117 mechanism involved in corrosion of the WE43 alloy. Based on this, the formation of the protective
118 coatings on the surface of the WE43 alloy and their corrosion resistance should also be examined.
119 The aim of this work was to investigate the physicochemical properties and corrosion performance
120 of inorganic, organic, and mixed inorganic-organic coatings on the surface of the WE43 alloy in
121 Hank's solution and evaluate their corrosion mechanisms. Three types of coatings, a conventional
122 phosphate conversion coating (CaP), an organic PLA coating, and a combined CaP-PLA coating

123 were obtained on the surface of the magnesium alloy WE43. The properties of as-treated samples
124 were comparatively investigated in Hank's solution through immersion and electrochemical
125 impedance spectroscopy (EIS) tests. Special attention has been paid to the spectroscopic
126 examination of the coatings after long-term exposure to Hank's solution, which is rarely reported
127 in the literature but is important in the understanding of their degradation profile.

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129 **2. Experimental**

130 **2.1. Materials and sample preparation**

131 The magnesium alloy WE43 containing rare-earth elements was used in this study. The
132 alloy was obtained according to the procedure reported elsewhere [50]. The chemical composition
133 of the as-obtained alloy was examined by an Axios PANalytical wavelength dispersive X-Ray
134 fluorescence spectrometer and is given in Table 1. The obtained plate material was cut into
135 specimens with sizes of about 20 mm × 20 mm × 5 mm. Before experiments, the samples were
136 mechanically ground with P800–P2000 grit emery paper in 96% ethanol. After every step, the
137 surface was ultrasonically cleaned for 5 min.

138 **Table 1.** Chemical composition of the used WE43 alloy based on X-Ray fluorescence analysis

Elemental composition [wt%]								
Al	Si	Y	Zr	Nd	Gd	Dy	Yb	Mg
0.01	0.09	4.8	0.7	2.9	0.4	0.3	0.08	Balance

139

140 As a source of PLA, Ingeo Biopolymer 3D850 from NatureWorks was used. All other
141 chemicals used in this study were obtained from LabInvest (Belarus) or PolAura (Poland) and
142 were of analytical reagent grade. All used solutions were prepared with deionized water with 18.2–
143 20.0 MΩ resistivity.

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147 **2.2. Formation of coatings**

148 The formation of CaP coatings on the surface of the WE43 alloy was performed in the
149 solutions containing, mol/L: $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 - 0.2$; $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 - 0.2$; NaOH to pH 3. The temperature of the
150 solution was kept at $70 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The deposition time was 60 min, after that the samples were
151 removed from the deposition bath, rinsed under a flow of deionized water, and air-dried. In the
152 text of this contribution, these samples are further referred to as CaP.

153 The PLA coatings were deposited on the surface of as-ground WE43 alloy (samples
154 referred to as PLA) and the surface after the phosphate CaP coating was formed (samples referred
155 to as CaP-PLA). The deposition was performed by the vertical immersion method in the solution
156 containing 5% PLA dissolved in trichloromethane. The ejection speed was 60 mm/min. As-
157 obtained samples were dried for 48 h at ambient temperature.

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159 **2.3. Surface analysis**

160 The surface morphology and elemental composition of the WE43 samples before and after
161 corrosion experiments were investigated using a JSM-5610 LV scanning electron microscope
162 (SEM) equipped with a JED-2201 energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) system.

163 The phase analysis of the samples was performed using an X'Pert PRO PANalytical X-
164 ray diffractometer. The obtained diffraction patterns were processed using the Match! Software
165 and PDF-4 2022 reference base. The crystallinity index of the CaP coating was calculated based
166 on the ratio of the total area of crystalline reflexes to the total area of all reflexes. The lattice
167 parameters were calculated based on the Scherrer equation.

168 The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were acquired using a
169 ThermoFisher Scientific Nicolet iN 10 microscope.

170 The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed before and
171 after corrosion experiments using a Gamdata Scienta hemispherical analyzer SES R4000. The
172 non-monochromatic $\text{AlK}\alpha$ radiation (1486.6 eV) used to excite the photoelectrons was generated

173 by the anode operating at 12 kV and 15 mA. The spectra analysis was performed by CasaXPS
174 2.3.23 software after subtraction of the Shirley-type background and fitting the experimental curve
175 with a combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian lines of variable proportions (70:30). All obtained
176 spectra were charge-corrected to the carbon C 1s excitation (285.0 eV).

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178 **2.4. Corrosion measurements**

179 Corrosion experiments were performed in Hank's solution (pH 7.4) of the following
180 composition, g/L: NaCl – 8.0; KCl – 0.2; CaCl₂ – 0.14; MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.1; MgCl₂·6H₂O – 0.1;
181 Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O – 0.06; KH₂PO₄ – 0.06; NaHCO₃ – 0.35; and D-glucose – 1.0 g.

182 Electrochemical corrosion experiments were carried out on an Autolab PGSTAT302N
183 potentiostat/galvanostat. A traditional three-electrode setup was used. The working electrode was
184 mounted at the bottom of the cell to avoid the accumulation of hydrogen gas, which hinders the
185 measurement conditions. Potential values were recorded relative to a saturated Ag/AgCl reference
186 electrode, and a Pt-mesh served as a counter electrode. The surface area of all samples was 1 cm². EIS
187 measurements were carried out at the OCP over the frequency range from 10⁵ to 10⁻² Hz using a
188 sinusoidal perturbation amplitude of 10 mV. Prior to EIS experiments, the OCP was stabilized for 30
189 min.

190 The amount of the evolved hydrogen gas was measured as described elsewhere [55].
191 Briefly, the non-working surface of the sample was mounted in a cold setting epoxy and then was
192 exposed to Hank's solution in a test tube connected to one of communicating burettes. The amount
193 of hydrogen was measured by a change in the solution volume in two communicating burettes.
194 The monitoring of the solution pH during corrosion experiments was performed using a TitroLine
195 easy titration system.

196 All corrosion measurements were performed in a thermostat at 37±0.5 °C and were at least
197 triplicated.

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200 **3. Results and discussion**

201 **3.1. Microstructure characterization of WE43 alloy**

202 Figure 1 shows SEM images of the surface of the as-polished WE43 alloy. The
203 microstructure of the WE43 alloy consists of the Mg matrix with irregular-shaped intermetallic
204 particles (IMPs). These secondary phases are either small, single constituents with sizes of ca. 10–
205 20 μm or form agglomerates with sizes of up to 100 μm . Such microstructure is typical for the
206 WE43 alloy [56,57]. The results of the EDX analysis showed that the alloy matrix primarily
207 consists of magnesium with a low percentage of alloying elements (Figure 1a, area 1, Table 2).
208 The regions around IMPs are enriched in yttrium and neodymium (Figure 1a, region 2). The EDX
209 analysis of IMPs (Fig. 1, regions 3–10) revealed several types of Mg-rare earth intermetallics of
210 Mg-Nd, Mg-Zr, Mg-Y, Mg-Nd-Y, Mg-Gd-Nd-Dy, and Mg-Y-Gd-Nd-Dy types with varying
211 stoichiometry [58–61].

212 Surface elemental EDX maps showed that the alloy matrix is primarily composed of Mg
213 (Fig. 2). Alloying additives of Nb, Gd, and Dy are distributed almost uniformly in the formed
214 IMPs and their fraction is much higher than in the matrix. In the case of Y, the relative distribution
215 over the surface was more uniform.

217 **Fig. 1.** SEM images of as-polished WE43 surface. Labeled regions show spots of EDX analysis
218 reported in Table 2

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222 **Table 2.** EDX analysis of the surface of as-polished WE43 Mg alloy (Analyzed areas are marked
 223 in Fig. 1)

Spot #	Elemental composition [wt%]					
	Mg	Y	Zr	Nd	Gd	Dy
WE43 surface	93.7	3.9	0.4	1.6	0.3	0.1
1	99.7	0.2	–	0.1	–	–
2	98.7	0.9	–	0.4	–	–
3	89.4	3.1	–	3.3	2.2	2.0
4	67.0	16.1	–	9.4	3.4	4.1
5	81.6	–	18.4	–	–	–
6	78.2	–	–	17.0	4.0	0.8
7	81.9	6.6	–	8.0	1.6	1.8
8	78.3	15.5	–	6.2	–	–
9	63.7	22.6	–	6.8	2.6	4.3
10	82.9	–	–	17.1	–	–

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226 **Fig. 2.** Surface EDX elemental maps of as-polished WE43 alloy

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231 **3.2. Characterization of deposited coatings**

232 **3.2.1 Microstructure and morphology**

233 The SEM images of the coated WE43 Mg alloy specimens are shown in Fig. 3.
234 Modification of the WE43 surface in PLA solution resulted in the formation of a uniform surface
235 layer without visible cracks or microdefects (Fig. 3a). The deposited CaP layer (Fig. 3b) is
236 characterized by a dense fine-grained crystalline structure with a mixed morphology. The surface
237 consists of small crystals together with a few up to ca. 50 μm -long scattered coarse crystals. The
238 whole surface was covered with coating and no visible gaps were detected during the analysis. The
239 CaP-PLA coating obtained in a two-stage process possessed a double-layered structure with a
240 bottom CaP layer and a top PLA layer (Fig. 3c). The formed PLA layer fully covered the bottom
241 CaP layer with only some visible spots where crystals of the CaP layer were protruding the top
242 polymer coating. The EDX analysis (Table 3) showed that the formed CaP layer consists of
243 calcium, phosphorus, and oxygen without a detectable signal from the substrate. The PLA and
244 CaP-PLA coatings contained carbon, oxygen, and chlorine with similar elemental compositions.
245 This may indicate that a continuous PLA coating was formed over the CaP sublayer (Fig. 3c). The
246 presence of chlorine in the composition of these coatings is explained by the use of chloroform as
247 a solvent of PLA.

248
249 **Fig. 3.** SEM images of surface morphology of (a) PLA, (b) CaP, and (c) CaP-PLA coatings

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254 **Table 3.** EDX analysis of the surface of WE43 Mg alloy with obtained CaP, PLA, and CaP-PLA
 255 coatings (examined area $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$)

Sample	Elemental composition [wt%]										
	Mg	Zr	Y	Nd	Gd	Dy	Ca	P	O	C	Cl
WE43	93.7	0.4	3.9	1.6	0.3	0.1	–	–	–	–	–
CaP	–	–	1.7	–	–	–	44.4	22.2	31.7	–	–
PLA	0.3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	41.5	56.3	2.2
CaP-PLA	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	41.5	55.9	2.6

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257 Figure 4 shows SEM images and EDX elemental maps of cross-sections of the WE43 alloy
 258 coated with CaP and CaP-PLA coatings. Some defects on the substrate-coating interface can
 259 originate from the samples preparation due to polishing and reaction of the substrate with the
 260 polishing medium (96% ethanol). In the case of the CaP-PLA layers, the presence of two distinct
 261 layers was observed based on the image contrast. In both coatings, the thickness of the formed
 262 CaP layer varied in the range from 10 to 20 μm . The elemental composition of the phosphate layer
 263 is uniform throughout the coating thickness and mainly consists of Ca and P. Nevertheless, a small
 264 amount of yttrium detected in the PLA coating during the top-surface EDX analysis (Table 3) may
 265 originate from the partial dissolution of yttrium in the deposition solution and the formation of its
 266 poorly soluble oxide [60]. The thickness of the polymer layer in CaP-PLA coating is about 20 μm .
 267 The top polymer layer has good adhesion to the inner CaP layer without visible structural defects
 268 (air pockets, cracks, delamination). Note, that the thickness of both CaP and PLA coatings may
 269 slightly vary over the surface of the samples due to the heterogeneity of the surface and used
 270 deposition approaches.

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3.2.2 Composition and deposition mechanism

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Fig. 4. SEM cross-cut images and EDX elemental maps of CaP (a) and CaP-PLA (b) coatings on WE43 Mg alloy

To understand the formation mechanism of CaP, PLA, and CaP-PLA coatings on the surface of the WE43 Mg alloy, their phase composition was examined. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the as-polished WE43 alloy and coated samples are shown in Fig. 5a. For the as-polished WE43 alloy, recorded reflexes correspond well to the alloy matrix (α -Mg, JCPDS card # 00-035-0821). Two reflexes of small intensity located at 2θ of 29.7° and 67.3° were assigned to $Mg_{41}Nd_5$ IMPs (JCPDS card # 00-035-0821). In the case of the PLA sample, the obtained diffractogram was identical to that of the WE43 alloy. However, a very broad low-intense peak was observed at 2θ $10\text{--}20^\circ$ during the analysis of enlarged images (not shown), which might be attributed to the amorphous PLA layer [62]. After deposition of the CaP coating, additional reflexes appeared on the XRD patterns of CaP and CaP-PLA samples, which were assigned to anhydrous (monetite, JCPDS card # 00-003-0398) and dihydrated (brushite, JCPDS card # 00-011-0293) $CaHPO_4$ phases [63,64]. For the individual CaP layer, calculation of the ratio of the crystalline part of the coating to its total fraction gave crystallinity degree of 52.6%. indicates that more than half of the coating mass has an ordered crystalline structure. The obtained value confirms the structural stability of the coating. Calculated phase parameters for the main monetite phase are: crystallite size 29.93 nm, dislocation density 0.0013 1/nm^2 . A low dislocation density

293 indicates a high structural stability of the coating, which can contribute to its durability and
 294 resistance to mechanical loads. Based on the change in the angle of the diffraction maximum, the
 295 microstrain parameter of the phosphate coating is $4.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$. A low microstrain value indicates the
 296 absence of significant internal stresses in the structure of the phosphate coating, which confirms
 297 its structural stability and high quality. An increase in the duration of the coating deposition at 60–
 298 100°C in aqueous solutions results in the transformation of the brushite phase into the monetite
 299 phase. No diffraction peaks corresponding to hydroxyapatite phases were indexed, which is in a
 300 good agreement with other studies [64–66]. It might be explained by the dissolution of the α -Mg
 301 matrix in the deposition bath and inhibition of hydroxyapatite growth by Mg ions [67].

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304 **Fig. 5.** (a) XRD patterns and (b) FTIR spectra of obtained PLA, CaP, and CaP-PLA coatings.

305 Reference XRD patterns of used JCPDS cards are given in the supplementary information

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307 The FTIR spectra of as-deposited coatings are shown in Fig. 5b. For PLA and CaP-PLA
 308 samples FTIR spectra were almost identical. The band at 752 cm^{-1} was assigned to vibrations of
 309 CH_2 group. Bands in the range of $868\text{--}990$ and $1084\text{--}1140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are characteristic of symmetric
 310 and asymmetric C–O–C vibrations and the band at 1045 cm^{-1} corresponds to stretching vibrations
 311 of C–O–C bonds of aliphatic esters. The band at 868 cm^{-1} indicates the formation of ordered PLA
 312 layers [68]. The band at 1184 cm^{-1} is associated with the stretching vibration of the C–O bond.

313 Bands in the range $1200\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are characteristic of C–O–C bond vibrations. The band at
 314 1755 cm^{-1} indicates the stretching vibration of the C=O carbonyl group. The band at 1454 cm^{-1}
 315 was assigned to CH_3 bending vibration. Bands at 2850 and 2928 cm^{-1} correspond to stretching
 316 vibrations in the CH_3 group [69].

317 The FTIR spectrum of the CaP coating exhibited vibrations in the region of $830\text{--}1160\text{ cm}^{-1}$
 318 $^{-1}$, which are typical for phosphates. A broad band in the range ca. $830\text{--}920\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned
 319 to symmetrical stretching of HPO_4^{2-} . [64,70] The band at 990 cm^{-1} corresponds to PO_4^{3-}
 320 antisymmetric stretching, while bands at 1063 and 1127 arise from PO_4^{3-} bending [64,71–73].

321 To further analyze the chemical states of the surface of all samples, XPS analysis was
 322 performed and its results are summarized in Fig. 6.

323
 324 **Fig. 6.** High-resolution XPS spectra of as-polished WE43 alloy and obtained PLA, CaP, and CaP-
 325 PLA coatings in the binding energy range of (a) C 1s, (b) O 1s, (c) Mg 1s, and (d) P 2p
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327 The high-resolution spectra obtained in the C 1s region (Fig. 6a) were deconvoluted into
 328 four components except for the CaP sample, where three components were extracted. The first
 329 component $C_{(1)}$ located at 285.0 eV , assigned to C–C/C–H bonds in organic compounds and
 330 contaminations [74], was found in all samples. This component is mainly associated with surface
 331 contamination [75]. The second component, $C_{(2)}$, located at 286.7 eV and $C_{(2)}^*$ at 285.9 eV were

332 assigned to C=O and C–O bonding, respectively. The next components, marked as C₍₃₎ and C₍₃₎*
333 located at 289.0 and 288.2 eV, respectively, were assigned to O–C=O groups. In the case of the
334 PLA and CaP-PLA samples, this component corresponds to the PLA layer [76]. For the CaP
335 sample, it is assigned to -COO-Ca [77] and most probably originated from surface contamination.
336 The last component, C₍₄₎, located at 290.1 eV, originated from the surface contamination of
337 carbonates.

338 The high-resolution O 1s spectra (Fig. 6b) were deconvoluted into several components.
339 Components O₍₁₎, O₍₂₎, and O₍₂₎*, located at 529.4, 530.9, and 531.5 eV, respectively, were
340 assigned to oxides, mostly MgO (components O₍₂₎, and O₍₂₎*). The component O₍₃₎ at 532.3 eV
341 corresponds to OH-groups in Mg(OH)₂ [75]. The last component O₍₄₎ at 533.5 eV was observed
342 on the surface of the PLA and CaP-PLA samples and corresponds to the C–O bonds in the PLA
343 layer [78].

344 The signal in the binding energy range of Mg 1s was detected only for WE43 and CaP
345 samples (Fig. 6c). The main Mg₍₁₎ component at 1304.1 eV for the WE43 sample was assigned to
346 Mg(OH)₂. A smaller component Mg₍₂₎ (1306.3 eV) was assigned to magnesium carbonate [79].
347 For the CaP sample, the main component Mg₍₃₎ (1304.3 eV) was identified as a signal from
348 magnesium phosphates/Mg(OH)₂.

349 The P 2p spectrum for the CaP sample was deconvoluted into one doublet with P 2p_{3/2} and
350 P 2p_{1/2} binding energies of 133.2 and 134.1 eV (marked as P and P', respectively), assigned to
351 phosphates (Fig. 6d). In the case of the CaP-PLA sample, the surface was fully covered by the
352 PLA layer and no signal of P was detected.

353 The results of FTIR and XPS experiments suggest higher amount of CH₃ groups of PLA
354 on the surface of CaP-PLA samples (increased intensity of FTIR bands at 2850 and 2928 cm⁻¹ in
355 Fig. 5b) and lower amount of C=O groups (decreased intensity of FTIR band at 1755 cm⁻¹ in Fig.
356 5b) comparing to a single PLA layer. It is also supported by the XPS spectra of O (Fig. 6b) and C
357 (Fig. 6c), where a lower amount of C₃ (O–C=O) and O₄ (C–O) components were registered for

358 CaP-PLA coatings. This suggests different mechanisms of the adhesion of PLA to the blank WE43
 359 substrate and CaP-coated substrate during the deposition process.

360 The obtained experimental data were supplemented by theoretical calculations. Fig. 7
 361 represents the equilibrium concentration diagram of ionic species and the volume fraction diagram
 362 of phosphate ions in the solution for the deposition of CaP coating. Calculations were performed
 363 without applying external potential, simulating fractions of the components corresponding to the
 364 aqueous conditions. However, it was assumed that Mg^{2+} ions are present in the solution due to the
 365 oxidation of the WE43 alloy. The concentration diagram (Fig. 7a) shows that several types of
 366 calcium and magnesium phosphates can be formed in the solution, while at very low pH aqueous
 367 Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions predominate. A more detailed fraction diagram for phosphate ions (Fig. 7b)
 368 revealed that soluble monocalcium phosphate $CaH_2PO_4^+$ ions will predominate in the pH range up
 369 to ca. 3.2. From pH ca. 2.9 the fraction of insoluble hydrated calcium phosphate $CaHPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$
 370 starts to increase and it is the most expected compound in the range of pH up to ca 6.2. At near-
 371 neutral conditions, mainly $Ca_5(PO_4)_3OH$ compound is expected. As Mg^{2+} ions were also
 372 considered in calculations, a minor fraction of $MgH_2PO_4^+$ ions in the pH range up to 6.5 and
 373 $MgHPO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ starting from pH ca. 5.6 can be expected.

374
 375 **Fig. 7.** (a) Concentration diagram and (b) volume fraction diagram of phosphate ions for
 376 an aqueous solution containing 0.2 M PO_4^{3-} , 0.2 M Ca^{2+} , and 0.01 M Mg^{2+} ions as a function of
 377 pH. No external potential was applied in calculations. The data were calculated using the Medusa
 378 software [80]

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380 Based on the experimental results and theoretical calculations, a formation mechanism of
 381 the CaP layer on the surface of the WE43 alloy can be described as follows. Upon immersion of
 382 the WE43 alloy in the deposition bath (pH 3), the surface of the Mg alloy dissolves rapidly
 383 according to the scheme:

386 The process generates excessive amounts of gaseous hydrogen. Consumption of H^+ on
 387 Eq. (2) results in local alkalization of the Mg alloy/electrolyte interface and an increase in pH.
 388 According to the thermodynamic data (Fig. 7), this would trigger the reaction of metal ions with
 389 H_2PO_4^- and the formation of insoluble $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the surface:

391 Our experimental data also indicated that anhydrous CaHPO_4 can be formed on the surface
 392 according to the equation:

394 Taking into account solubility product constants, K_{sp} , of CaHPO_4 (2.7×10^{-7}), $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot$
 395 $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.6×10^{-7}) [81], and MgHPO_4 (1.2×10^{-3}) [65] it is expected that only calcium phosphates
 396 will be included in the formed coating.

397 The remnant H_2PO_4^- ions can also react with OH^- to form HPO_4^{2-} and then PO_4^{3-} ions,
 398 which can form insoluble salts $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Mg}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [82]:

401

402 **3.3 Corrosion in Hank's solution**

403 The corrosion properties of the WE43 alloy with and without surface modification were
 404 evaluated in Hank's solution.

405 The results of the EIS measurements in the form of Nyquist plots are shown in Fig. 8. The
 406 impedance response of the bare WE43 alloy in Hank's solution (Fig. 8a) is typical for this type of
 407 Mg alloys [57]. The Nyquist plot characteristically displayed one small capacitive loop at high

408 frequencies, a large depressed capacitive loop at medium to low frequencies, and an inductive tail
 409 at low frequencies. The capacitive response is associated with the charge transfer processes, while
 410 the inductive response is typically associated with relaxation processes of adsorbed charged
 411 corrosion intermediates [83]. In the case of coated samples (Fig. 8b), impedance spectra showed
 412 two capacitive semicircles without inductive region, which indicates better corrosion resistance of
 413 the surface. The best corrosion resistance was provided by CaP-PLA coating. To quantitatively
 414 analyze the EIS data, equivalent circuits shown in Fig. 8c were used. In these circuits, the constant
 415 phase element CPE, with two parameters, the CPE constant Y and the exponent n obtained from
 416 the data fitting, was used. Other circuit's elements include R_s as the solution resistance, CPE_1 as
 417 the capacitive response of the surface film (coating or corrosion products), R_2 as the surface film
 418 resistance, CPE_2 as the double-layer capacitive response, and R_3 as the charge transfer resistance
 419 [57,83]. Circuit 1 used for the bare WE43 alloy additionally contains L_1 and R_1 elements, which
 420 are the inductance and resistance parameters involving adsorbed intermediates that give rise to the
 421 impedance response at low frequencies. The quantitative assessment of the surface resistance was
 422 performed based on the values of the polarization resistance, R_p , calculated as shown in Fig. 8c.
 423 The obtained fit parameters and calculated R_p values are summarized in Table 4.

424

425 **Fig. 8.** Nyquist EIS plots in Hank's solution of WE43 alloy (a) and obtained PLA, CaP, and CaP-
 426 PLA coatings (b). Symbols represent experimental data and lines are results of spectra fitting using
 427 equivalent circuits shown in (c)

428

429 From the fitting results (Table 4), the highest value of R_p was observed for a two-layer
 430 CaP-PLA coating. The high protective ability of the CaP-PLA coating most probably originates
 431 from two factors: i) different adhesion of the PLA layer to the CaP layer as compared to the
 432 untreated WE43 alloy (Table S1 and Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Information), and ii) filling of
 433 CaP microcracks with the polymer layer, which further prevents direct contact of the corrosive
 434 medium with the magnesium substrate. However, it should be noted that these values were
 435 extracted from two different circuits so caution should be taken in the direct comparison of the
 436 quantitative data [84]. Moreover, electrochemical methods can overestimate the corrosion
 437 resistance of Mg alloys [55,83,85]. Therefore, hydrogen evolution and pH of Hank's solution were
 438 monitored for 14 days.

439

440 **Table 4.** Fitting data extracted from EIS data

Sample	L / H cm^2	R_1 / Ω cm^2	$Y_1 / \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^n$	n_1	$R_2 / \Omega \text{cm}^2$	$Y_2 / \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^n$	n_2	$R_3 / \Omega \text{cm}^2$	$R_p / \Omega \text{cm}^2$
WE43	41.9 ± 5.7	534.4 \pm 28.1	(7.2 \pm 2.7) $\cdot 10^{-5}$	0.81 \pm 0.11	224. 2 \pm 34.8	(1.8 \pm 0.3) $\cdot 10^{-3}$	0.80 \pm 0.15	12.9 \pm 4.7	164.2
CaP	–	–	(1.4 \pm 0.3) $\cdot 10^{-5}$	0.70 \pm 0.09	5793.4 \pm 148.2	(3.9 \pm 1.8) $\cdot 10^{-4}$	0.82 \pm 0.07	2894.4 \pm 58.1	8687.8
PLA	–	–	(6.4 \pm 1.6) $\cdot 10^{-9}$	0.84 \pm 0.12	16543.7 \pm 2534.9	(1.4 \pm 0.6) $\cdot 10^{-5}$	0.60 \pm 0.05	52866.0 \pm 12573.7	69409.7
CaP- PLA	–	–	(1.8 \pm 0.4) $\cdot 10^{-9}$	0.88 \pm 0.05	79859.1 \pm 5024.0	(6.6 \pm 2.3) $\cdot 10^{-6}$	0.67 \pm 0.18	148510.2 \pm 22455.0	228369.3

441

442 The results of the hydrogen evolution test are shown in Fig. 9. The volume of hydrogen
 443 evolved in Hank's solution containing bare WE43 alloy gradually increased with time. After 5
 444 days, the hydrogen release rate decreased slightly, which may be a sign of the partial surface
 445 passivation by corrosion products. In the case of treated samples, the volume of the evolved
 446 hydrogen significantly decreased. In the case of CaP and CaP-PLA coatings almost no hydrogen
 447 was evolved during 14 days of the experiment. This indicates the high protective ability of the
 448 formed coatings.

449 In near-neutral Hank's solution (initial pH 7.4 ± 0.2), corrosion of the WE43 Mg alloy
 450 consists of the anodic dissolution of Mg matrix (Eq. (1)) and the cathodic reaction of hydrogen
 451 evolution (Eq. (7)):

452 with the overall reaction (Eq. (8))

453 Therefore, the evolution of hydrogen is possible when the substrate is in contact with Hank's
 454 solution. In the case of a single PLA layer its degradation results in fast contact of the Mg substrate
 455 with the solution. Oppositely, in the case of the CaP-PLA layer, hydrogen evolution will be
 456 initiated only after degradation of both PLA and CaP layers. That is the main reason for the
 457 improved corrosion resistance.
 458
 459

460
 461 **Fig. 9.** Hydrogen evolution as a function of the immersion time of WE43 alloy and obtained PLA,
 462 CaP, and CaP-PLA coatings in Hank's solution

463

464 Figure 10 shows the dependence of the change in the pH of Hank's solution on the exposure
 465 time of the investigated WE43 alloy specimens. The microstructure of the WE43 alloy consists of
 466 the Mg matrix with irregular-shaped IMPs (Figs. 1, 2), and these IMPs are cathodic relative to the
 467 Mg matrix [57]. Owing to a large difference in the Volta-potentials [57], galvanic corrosion caused
 468 by the second phases usually dominates in the corrosion rate of Mg alloys [86,87]. Magnesium
 469 ions Mg^{2+} formed by Eq. (1) can interact with hydroxide-ions formed by Eq. (7) to produce poorly
 470 soluble magnesium hydroxide $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. Therefore, the change in the pH of the corrosive medium

471 associated with the occurrence of the cathodic process on Eq. (8) can be used as a measure of the
 472 corrosion rate of magnesium alloys. In the case of the untreated WE43 alloy, the pH of the
 473 electrolyte gradually increased reaching the value of 10.4 after 14 days of exposure. The PLA
 474 sample showed a very similar trend of the change in the pH with time, indicating poor long-term
 475 corrosion resistance of the single PLA layer, despite the rather high protective ability obtained in
 476 the EIS experiments (Fig. 8, Table 4). In turn, the pH of Hank's solution where CaP and CaP-PLA
 477 coatings were exposed did not increase so prominently. According to the literature [87,88],
 478 phosphate conversion coatings preferentially precipitate on the cathodic sites of the surface,
 479 effectively suppressing the cathodic reaction. The pH of the Hank's solution increased for the first
 480 three days of the experiment and then almost did not change, reaching the value of 8.7 and 7.9
 481 after 14 days of exposure of the CaP and CaP-PLA samples in Hank's solution, respectively. This
 482 indicates a high corrosion resistance of CaP and especially combined CaP-PLA coatings.

483

484 **Fig. 10.** Evolution of pH of Hank's solution during 14 days of exposure of WE43 Mg alloy with
 485 different surface treatment

486

487 3.4 Post-corrosion surface analysis

488 For a more detailed examination of the protective properties, a post-corrosion analysis of
 489 the surface of the obtained coatings was carried out after 14 days of exposure to Hank's solution.

490 The results of the XRD analysis of all examined samples after 14 days of exposure to
 491 Hank's solution are presented in Fig. 11a. The most significant changes were observed for the

492 WE43 and PLA samples. In both cases, new strong reflexes corresponding to $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ (JCPDS
 493 card # 00-044-1482) were observed on the XRD patterns. Diffractograms of the CaP and CaP-
 494 PLA samples were similar to those shown in Fig. 5a for as-obtained samples.

495
 496 **Fig. 11.** (a) XRD patterns and (b) FTIR spectra of PLA, CaP, and CaP-PLA coatings after 14 days
 497 of exposure to Hank's solution. Reference XRD patterns of used JCPDS cards are given in the
 498 supplementary information

499
 500 The FTIR spectra of the coatings after 14 days of corrosion in Hank's solution are shown
 501 in Fig. 11b. The general appearance of the spectra remained similar for all specimens. For the PLA
 502 and CaP-PLA coatings, an increase in the intensity of the bands at 1278 and 1184 cm^{-1} associated
 503 with asymmetric C–O–C stretching vibrations and asymmetric CH_3 vibrations is observed. Such
 504 changes can be explained by an increase in the crystallinity of the PLA coating [89,90]. The
 505 appearance of the band at 1550 cm^{-1} corresponds to O_2 vibrations. In the case of the CaP coating,
 506 an additional wide band at $1620\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed, which is due to the presence of OH-
 507 groups of water. Spectra of all samples also show wide bands in the region $3670\text{--}3020\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which
 508 correspond to the stretching vibrations of OH- groups of water.

509 To further evaluate changes in the surface chemistry after long-term corrosion analysis,
 510 XPS spectra were recorded. Due to the high amount of water adsorbed by the PLA sample, it was

511 not possible to reach the level of vacuum in the equipment chamber required for the XPS
 512 measurement. Therefore, Fig. 12 shows the results for WE43, CaP, and CaP-PLA samples only.

513
 514 **Fig. 12.** High-resolution XPS spectra in the binding energy range of (a) C 1s, (b) O 1s, (c) Mg 1s,
 515 and (d) P 2p of WE43 alloy, CaP, and CaP-PLA coatings after corrosion experiments in Hank's
 516 solutions

517
 518 The general appearance of C 1s spectra (Fig. 12a) and components assignment remained
 519 the same as for the as-obtained samples (Fig. 6a). For the WE43 sample, the relative fraction of
 520 the C₍₄₎ component increased significantly, indicating higher surface amounts of magnesium
 521 carbonate and intensive corrosion of the alloy in Hank's solution. For CaP and CaP-PLA samples,
 522 the most notable increase in the surface fraction corresponded to the C_{(2)*} component, assigned to
 523 C–O bonding. In the high-resolution O 1s spectra (Fig. 12b), O₍₁₎ became the main component for
 524 WE43 and CaP samples. For the CaP-PLA sample, O₍₁₎ and O₍₂₎ remained the main components.
 525 The XPS spectra of the WE43 and CaP samples contained additional component O₍₃₎ at 532.6 eV,
 526 which was assigned to OH- groups or absorbed water. The Mg 1s spectrum for the WE43 sample
 527 possessed a new component Mg₍₄₎ located at 1304.3 eV and associated with Mg(OH)₂ (Fig. 12c)
 528 [55]. The P 2p spectrum (Fig. 12d) was similar to that before corrosion experiments. Summarizing,
 529 the surface chemistry of the WE43 alloy changed significantly due to the corrosion attack, while

530 the surface of modified samples remained almost the same, indicating their high corrosion
531 resistance.

532 The post-corrosion morphologies of the untreated WE43 alloy and coated samples are
533 shown in Fig. 13. A thick layer of corrosion products was formed on the surface of the WE43
534 sample (Fig. 13a). This surface layer is non-uniform and contains a network of microcracks, due
535 to the release of hydrogen and the internal stresses. The layer itself could not provide reliable
536 corrosion protection of the substrate. The formation of wedge-shaped cracks can be explained by
537 stress concentration at the top layer of dislocations near the grain boundary of the alloy. The
538 surface of the CaP sample after 14 days of exposure to the Hank's solution (Fig. 13b) did not
539 undergo significant morphological changes. The surface of the samples coated with PLA (Fig.
540 13c) had two characteristic surface regions. The first one, clearly visible at smaller magnifications
541 represents the surface regions covered with corrosion products. The second one appears as a
542 network of micropores, which indicates polymer degradation in Hank's solution. Such a
543 morphology supports the results of the pH monitoring (Fig. 10), confirming the low corrosion
544 resistance of the PLA film. In the case of the CaP-PLA sample (Fig. 13d), the morphology of the
545 top surface layer was similar to the PLA sample and revealed degradation of the polymer layer.
546 The formed pores were larger in diameter and the bottom CaP layer was visible in some spots.
547 However, the surface was clear from corrosion products, since the bottom CaP layer remained
548 intact.

549 The point EDX analysis (Table 5) of the selected surface regions (marked in Fig. 13)
550 showed that the layer of corrosion products formed on the surface of the untreated WE43 Mg alloy
551 (Table 5, spot 1) is rich in Mg and O, supporting deposition of an oxide-hydroxide layer of
552 corrosion products on the surface. The presence of P and Ca indicates that this layer also contains
553 poorly soluble calcium and magnesium phosphates, originating from the composition of the
554 Hank's solution. The composition of the CaP surface (Table 5, point 2) practically did not change
555 during corrosion testing and is comparable to the initial sample (Table 3). The elemental

556 composition of PLA and CaP-PLA samples is presented by mostly C and O, with minor amounts
 557 of P and Cl. In the case of the PLA sample, spots identified as corrosion products contained high
 558 amounts of Na and Cl, suggesting severe corrosion attack in these regions.

559
 560 **Fig. 13.** SEM images of surface morphology of (a) untreated WE43, (b) CaP, (c) PLA, and (d)
 561 CaP-PLA coatings after 14 days of exposure to Hank's solution. Arrows indicate regions of point
 562 EDX analysis listed in Table 5

563
 564 **Table 5.** Point EDX analysis of the surface of WE43 Mg alloy without and with obtained CaP,
 565 PLA, and CaP-PLA coatings after 14 days of exposure to Hank's solution (examined points are
 566 marked in Fig. 13)

Point of analysis	Elemental composition [wt%]										
	Mg	Y	Nd	Gd	Dy	Ca	P	O	C	Cl	Na
1	32.9	1.3	5.0	1.4	0.9	1.4	12.8	38.3	–	–	–
2	17.4	0.6	0.1	–	–	16.7	11.9	48.2	–	–	5.1
3	0.9	–	–	–	–	–	0.2	41.8	55.6	1.6	
4	0.5	–	–	–	–	–	0.2	15.7	48.7	6.5	28.4
5	0.3	–	–	–	–	2.1	1.5	42.9	52.4	0.9	–

6	-	-	-	-	-	0.1	0.2	42.0	55.7	1.1	-
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567

568 Figure 14 shows SEM cross-cut images of the examined samples after 14 days of corrosion
569 testing in Hank's solution. The layer of corrosion products formed on the surface of the untreated
570 WE43 Mg alloy (Fig. 14a) has a thickness of about 15 μm . The cracks observed in the top-surface
571 SEM observations (Fig. 13a) reach the metal substrate. Interestingly, the results of the point EDX
572 analysis confirmed that the layer of corrosion products also contains inclusions rich in Y, Gd,
573 Dy, and Nd (Fig. 14a, point 1, Table 6), which are alloying elements in the WE43 alloy and form
574 IMPs in its microstructure. In the case of the CaP coating (Fig. 14b) the layer morphology did not
575 reveal significant changes. However, cross-cut observations revealed the presence of a local
576 corrosion attack similar to filiform corrosion. The best results were obtained for the CaP-PLA
577 sample, which does not undergo visible structural changes after 14 days of corrosion (Fig. 14d).

578

579 **Fig. 14.** SEM cross-cut images of (a) untreated WE43, (b) CaP, (c) PLA, and (d) CaP-PLA
580 coatings after 14 days of exposure to Hank's solution

581 Mechanisms of corrosion degradation of the obtained coatings are schematically illustrated
582 in Fig. 15. The results of the corrosion experiments confirmed that the most severe corrosion attack
583 was observed for the untreated WE43 alloy. In this case, the Mg matrix of the alloy is dissolved,

584 while the most severe corrosion attack is initiated and proceeds along the Mg matrix/IMPs
 585 interface due to galvanic coupling [57,91]. The mechanism of the destruction of cathodic IMPs
 586 containing rare-earth elements is not so straightforward and the most expected mechanism is the
 587 one similar to the iron re-deposition explained in several previous studies [92–94]. Briefly,
 588 cathodic IMPs are first detached from the metallic substrate by undermining or hydrogen bubbles
 589 due to the process described by Eq. (7). Later on, rare-earth-rich particles are dissolved in the
 590 electrolyte forming soluble compounds, which are then reduced to metallic rare-earth or react with
 591 the solution compounds (for example, phosphates) to form insoluble precipitates.

592

593 **Table 6.** Point EDX analysis of the crosscut areas of WE43 Mg alloy without and with CaP
 594 coatings after 14 days of exposure to Hank’s solution (examined points are marked in Fig. 14)

Point of analysis	Elemental composition [wt%]							
	Mg	Y	Nd	Gd	Dy	Ca	P	O
1	77.4	8.7	7.8	2.2	3.9	1.4	7.9	–
2	76.8	15.4	3.9	1.5	2.4	–	–	–
3	44.2	–	–	–	–	0.3	9.9	–
4	40.0	–	–	–	–	38.2	21.8	–
5	43.3	2.3	1.3	–	–	0.2	1.2	51.8

595

596 The corrosion mechanism was different in the case when CaP and/or PLA coatings were
 597 deposited on the surface. In these cases, the WE43 alloy surface was protected by the formed
 598 coatings. However, individual coatings possess local corrosion spots. In the case of the CaP layer,
 599 these spots were up to 20 μm deep and hidden under the CaP layer. The occurrence of such
 600 corrosion spots can be explained by the presence of microcracks in the CaP structure, where
 601 contact of the metal matrix with the electrolyte is possible.

602 The low protective ability of the PLA coating can be explained by its high water
 603 permeability. Consequently, during long-term corrosion, a corrosive medium can reach the
 604 metallic substrate, which leads to the initiation of corrosion under the polymer film. At the same
 605 time, the obtained PLA layer retained its integrity, and no delamination was observed.

607

608 **Fig. 15.** Schematic representation of the formed layers before (to the left) and after (to the right)
 609 exposure to Hank's solution for 14 days

610

611 The best results were observed for the dual CaP-PLA coating. The improvement in the
 612 corrosion resistance is achieved by filling pores and cracks in the CaP layer with the top PLA
 613 coating, which is clearly seen on SEM images before (Fig. 3c) and after (Fig. 13d) corrosion tests.

614

615 4. Conclusions

616 In this work, the effect of surface pretreatment by a calcium phosphate and/or PLA layer
 617 on the corrosion properties of the WE43 magnesium alloy was examined. The high corrosion
 618 protection effectiveness of all coatings was observed and correlated with the surface film structure.

619 The following conclusions can be drawn:

620 1. SEM and EDX analysis revealed that the WE43 alloy has a complex microstructure,
621 which contains an Mg matrix and Mg-rare earth IMPs (Nd, Gd, Dy, Y, Zr).

622 2. A dense and fine-grained conversion CaP coating mainly consisting of $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
623 and CaHPO_4 with a thickness of 10–20 μm was formed on the surface of the WE43 alloy. The
624 corrosion rate of the as-treated WE43 alloy in Hank's solution decreased by a factor of 10. In the
625 long-term corrosion experiments, the CaP layer did not undergo significant structural,
626 morphological, and phase changes. However, due to local coating defects (cracks, pores), several
627 local corrosion spots were observed, which is in good accordance with an increase in the pH of
628 Hank's solution by ≈ 1.1 .

629 3. Deposition of the PLA layer on the surface of the WE43 alloy results in the formation
630 of a uniform polymer coating with a thickness of about 20 μm . The corrosion rate of the as-treated
631 WE43 alloy in Hank's solution decreased by a factor of 100. However, due to high water
632 permeability and low adhesion to the substrate, PLA coating does not provide reliable corrosion
633 protection of the WE43 substrate in long-term corrosion experiments.

634 4. A two-layer CaP-PLA coating provided reliable corrosion protection with corrosion
635 current density decreasing by a factor of 500 compared to the untreated WE43 alloy, and by a
636 factor of 53 compared to the CaP sample, which is explained by the filling of the local surface
637 defects in the bottom phosphate layer by the top polymer layer. After long-term corrosion tests in
638 Hank's solution, the two-layer coating did not show visible structural changes, and the pH of the
639 solution practically did not change in time, which indicates the high protective properties of the
640 CaP-PLA coating.

641 **Declarations of interest**

642 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
643 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

644

645

646 **Data availability**

647 The raw/processed data required to reproduce the findings of this study are available from
648 the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

649

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653

654 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

655 **Andrei V. Paspelau:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis,
656 Visualization, Validation, Writing – Original Draft;

657 **Aliaksandr A. Kasach:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis,
658 Visualization, Validation, Writing – Original Draft;

659 **Jacek Gurgul:** Investigation;

660 **Grzegorz Mordarski:** Investigation;

661 **Konrad Skowron:** Investigation;

662 **Irina I. Kurilo:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – Review & Editing;

663 **Dzmitry S. Kharytonau:** Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization,
664 Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation, Funding
665 acquisition, Supervision; Writing – Original Draft; Writing – Review & Editing.

666

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